

Exploration of Illegal, Unreported, Unregulated Fishing and Vessel Relationships using AIS Data and Machine Learning

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Abstract—Illegal, unreported, and unregulated (IUU) fishing is a key driver of global overfishing, threatens marine ecosystems, puts food security and regional stability at risk, and is linked to major human rights violations and even organized crime [8]. The ability to predict both where and when IUU fishing is likely occurring provides significant advantages to coast guards with limited resources. In this paper, we provide three resources to aid in the ability to identify IUU fishing. First, we created an algorithm to identify refrigeration ships that often meet with fishing vessels to transport the catch to port. Next, we explored the relationships between these vessels and ports. To do so, we displayed not only the traffic coming and going, but also the statistics surrounding the vessels next visited port via an interactive dashboard. Lastly, we explored an Item Response Theory (IRT) Model that bears a relationship between variables obtained from the fishing vessels’ AIS communication and probability that IUU fishing activity is occurring. We also created and used a Density Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN) model to explore areas where IUU fishing occurs most often. We approached the problem as an exploratory data problem, with the primary objective of understanding the significance of certain parameters, models, or instances of IUU activity in the data as an initial point of reference for future work.

Index Terms—IUU Fishing, Item Response Theory, Density Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise, Machine Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Illegal, unregulated, and unreported (IUU) fishing is any fishing activity, spanning a wide range, that violates national and/or international regulations. To further understand IUU fishing, it is beneficial to break it down into its distinctive definitions. The National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration defines illegal fishing as “any fishing activity conducted in contravention of applicable laws and regulations”, unreported fishing as “any fishing activity that is not report or are misreported to relevant authorities”, and unregulated fishing as “fishing in areas where there is no applicable conservation or management measures ... also unregulated when occurring in an RFMO-managed area and conducted by vessels without nationality, or by those flying a flag of a State or fishing entity that is not party to the RFMO” [8]. The

range of what constitutes IUU fishing is extremely large. Some IUU activities include, but are not limited to: overfishing, failure to report entirety of catch, fishing in another country’s exclusive economic zone (EEZ) without permission, fishing without a flag or the incorrect flag, transferring fish without authorization, or unlicensed border hopping.

IUU fishing is a major problem in undeveloped countries. These countries tend to have less resources, resulting in difficulty enforcing and protecting their EEZs. This research paper will focus on aspects of IUU fishing that can be detected from Automatic Identification Systems (AIS) data. We began our exploration by studying vessel relationships through identifying refrigeration and fishing vessel interactions as well as monitoring port traffic. Additionally, we investigated two different machine learning models to determine where and when IUU fishing is occurring. The preliminary results are promising and create a foundation for future work in the area.

II. RELATED WORK

Some of the work related to this subject at hand comes at the problem in different perspectives. The first perspective is using both Linear Regression and Random Forests to try and predict IUU fishing behavior. This work really focuses on using simple regression and tree techniques to build a model to predict IUU fishing [3]. While this perspective did lead to interesting results of 84% test accuracy on the test set, the data that was trained and tested on was around 1300 observations total [3]. The paper did not give much explanation as to what type of IUU cases that the researchers hoped to find, but it did provide a starting point for our research. This created a need to define the types of IUU cases we wanted to explore.

Another piece of work that is related to the subject comes from George Mason University [2]. Their research focused on IUU fishing, but they were able to approach the problem in many different ways. First, the team created a model to predict whether a certain vessel was fishing or not [2]. Next, they created a position model that looked to see if the vessel was near or in a restricted fishing zones, how many times the vessel was in port, and other attributes about the vessel’s position

[2]. Then, the team created a Bayesian Network to predict whether the vessel was engaging in IUU fishing based off of many different parameters including some from the position model and the fishing model [2]. This research was crucial to the contribution of the paper because it allowed the problem to be looked at in a different light.

III. BACKGROUND

A. Automatic Identification Systems Data

Fishing and cargo vessels travel around the world every day equipped with an Automatic Identification System (AIS) device [4]. This device sends data about the vessel to both terrestrial and satellite AIS receiver units. [4]. The AIS data that is collected includes the Maritime Mobile Service Identity (MMSI) number of the vessel, the ship's International Maritime Organization (IMO) number if applicable, the name or call sign of the vessel, the dimensions of the ship, the vessel type, the draught of the vessel, the destination of the vessel, the expected time of arrival of the vessel to its destination, and the route plan for the vessel [1]. This data comes in at regular intervals that ranges from every few seconds to every couple of minutes. However, most of the data is inputted manually by the crew, therefore it can be very unreliable at times. Some of the parameters that are received by the AIS system change frequently, such as the vessel's speed and direction, but are not updated regularly. Regularly updated categories include the latitude and longitude of the vessel, the timestamp of the communication, and course over ground [1].

B. EEZ Boundaries

A country's Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) is a 200 nautical mile radius around the ocean that belongs to a country [9]. The country has the right and permission to say who can fish and drill for oil in that zone [9]. Vessels can only fish in a country's EEZ if they are from the country or have a treaty with the country the vessel is from to fish in the home country's EEZ. When countries are not separated by 200 nautical miles they will create a smaller EEZ boundary, since 200 nautical miles is not feasible [9]. Some EEZ boundaries are claimed by multiple countries which causes political arguments.

C. Data Overview

The data used for this paper contained AIS communications of cargo and fishing vessels from February 2022 to February 2023 in the region of the South China Sea and into the Pacific Ocean. It also consisted of EEZ and port boundaries. Figure 1 shows the region of interest that we conducted the research in with the boundaries of the EEZs for the countries in the area. Figure 2 displays the locations of the ports inside the area of interest.

IV. VESSEL RELATIONSHIP EXPLORATION

The relationships between fishing vessels, refrigeration vessels (reefers), and ports are typically assumed at a high, simplified level. In standard fishing practices, fishing vessels

Fig. 1. Region of Interest with EEZs

Fig. 2. Ports in the Area of Interest

will meet reefers in open water, transfer their catch to the refrigeration ships, and continue fishing - whether it be elsewhere in the water or at the same location. This exchange between fishing vessels and reefers allows the fishing vessels to save time, fuel, and money - increasing their efficiency. Once a fishing vessel has completed fishing, or needs more fuel, they will likely return to port. From the point of contact with the fishing vessels, the reefers will return to port, bringing the fish back to land, and return to the water to reconvene with another fishing vessel.

There's a common assumption that these relationships are straightforward, but questions remain: how do these relationships present themselves? Do certain fishing vessels continually interact with the same reefer sets? How often do fishing vessels enter port? Do they, or reefers, operate out of a single, "preferred", port? These are just a few questions that we aimed to answer with the analysis with hope of further explaining the relationship between fishing vessels, reefers, and ports.

A. Refrigeration Vessel Identification Algorithm

To identify where and when these interactions between reefers and fishing vessels were happening, we designed an algorithm based on information given by the ship's AIS data. Due to the rapid output of AIS communications from ships the algorithm works best and runs in a timely manner when given a bounding box from the user. The corresponding bounding box

is then spilt horizontally into four sections with each section containing four Voronoi regions. The purpose of the sections and regions is to reduce complexity and allow for parallel processing to be utilized. Figure 3 shows an example bounding box that has been split into sections and regions.

Fig. 3. Bounding Box with Sections and Regions

After the bounding box is transformed, a shape file containing port information is turned into a data frame. The file provided contains polygons that encompass the area of the port, not single points. Now, the AIS ship data is brought in. The files are read in one at a time and undergo the following process. First, the data is cut into 20 minute overlapping windows. For example a list of windows might contain the following [10:00 - 10:20, 10:05 - 10:25 ...]. Next, the windows are looped through and each AIS communication is given a section and region corresponding to its latitude and longitude. The operations performed for every section and region combination are the same therefore we took advantage of parallel progressing to speed up the calculations.

1) Interaction Identification Processes:

- Determine the distance each cargo vessel traveled in the 20 minute window.
- Find the cargo ships that traveled less than 3.5 kilometers. Cargo vessels are less likely than fishing vessels to stop out in the ocean for reasons other than meeting another vessel.
- Determine if the cargo vessel is in port. Keep only the vessels outside of port.
- For the cargo vessels not in port, create a line connecting the AIS points that make up their path. Buffer the line by 800 meters to create a polygon.
- Determine if any fishing vessels were in the cargo vessels buffer for 12 or more minutes. If it was, classify as an interaction.
- If a fishing vessel was in the buffer but the time span was less than 12 minutes, store the MMSI pair with the earliest time into a dictionary. Or, check the dictionary to see if the MMSI pair is already in the dictionary and the time span has been equal to or greater than an hour. If the duration is equal to or over an hour, classify as an interaction.

2) *Creating the Final Data Frame:* Due to the overlapping windows and the extended nature of vessel meetings the outputted data frame involved many duplicate rows. To rectify this, a function was created to identify each unique interaction.

The max threshold for an interaction was set at 25 hours. This threshold was based on our initial results as well as a subject expert's opinion. We also thought it would be useful to easily be able to filter interactions that happen right outside of port versus ones that happen off the coastline of the country. Using an outline of the selected country we created a column that distinguishes between the two locations. Figure 4 shows an example of a final interaction data frame.

	Cargo_mmsi	Fishing_mmsi	Cargo_geo	fishing_points	start	duration	Location
2	372033000	412549016	POLYGON ((156.95643 43.38124, 156.95627 43.380...	<zip object at 0x7f0744944940>	2022-09-30 19:45:51	0 days 05:56:47	Outside the Coastline
3	273313270	273824600	POLYGON ((148.35793 44.91668, 148.35787 44.915...	<zip object at 0x7f06eb21ad80>	2022-09-30 22:09:03	0 days 12:46:49	Outside the Coastline
4	412549037	412440824	POLYGON ((154.65529 43.81967, 154.65515 43.819...	<zip object at 0x7f07509cd040>	2022-09-30 22:09:24	0 days 05:37:30	Outside the Coastline
5	416778000	416005877	POLYGON ((155.94677 44.05622, 155.94661 44.055...	<zip object at 0x7f07454592cd0>	2022-09-30 22:32:30	0 days 03:11:31	Outside the Coastline
6	412440834	412549375	POLYGON ((153.69923 43.54212, 153.69911 43.541...	<zip object at 0x7f06eb4dcd80>	2022-09-30 22:37:49	0 days 07:53:20	Outside the Coastline
7	412500000	412440478	POLYGON ((153.46659 43.20654, 153.46646 43.205...	<zip object at 0x7f06eb4dcdcd0>	2022-10-01 01:37:58	0 days 01:02:49	Outside the Coastline

Fig. 4. Final Interaction Data Frame

3) *Limitations:* We were able to prove that our algorithm does indeed find interactions accurately. Our output was compared to a list of interactions that was identified by a subject expert visually studying the data. The algorithm was able to find all of the sample interactions, with 2/3 of the duration's being within thirty minutes. The other interaction had a duration that was an hour and a half shorter due to the limitations of our algorithm. The main limitation of our algorithm is the reliance on AIS communications. AIS data is self-reported and therefore can be very unreliable. If a ship is involved in an interaction and does not emit an AIS communication until they leave, we will be unable to detect that interaction. Also, if their AIS communications are very sparse, it causes the duration to be less accurate. Secondly, our code is heavily based on the port boundaries and often areas right outside of port will show a lot of interactions, as ships are near each other entering and leaving. While these are not the interactions we are interested in, they can add additional value. We are able to identify ports that were not in the data set. Once identified, the ports were added to the port data set to help increase the accuracy of the interaction algorithm.

B. Port Traffic Information

After completing the interaction algorithm, we sought to collect information about the ports in which fishing and cargo vessels docked at. Using the port data set, which included bounding polygons for the port boundaries, we were able to classify AIS communications as in or out of port. Looking at

the pattern of classifications we could determine when a ship entered or exited port due to its classification changing. These classifications changes allowed us to determine both enter and exit times for the vessels. From the enter/exit times, we could easily obtain the duration that a vessel was "in port," and filter the results based on country, port or vessel.

Another relationship question we wanted to answer was what is the next port a vessel travels to after it leaves its current port. Using the already created data frame we created a new column called *next_port*. This column's value defaults to "None" if the ship is currently docked, or it has not yet entered a port after leaving the previous one. The next port information will self-update as new information is passed to the function that creates the data frame. From this information, we can observe the travel patterns of fishing and cargo ships, and frequency in which they visit certain ports.

mmsi	vessel_type	PORT_NAME	enter_time	exit_time	duration	next_port
431002141	Cargo	KATSUNAN	2022-09-30 18:00:16	2022-09-30 22:07:27	0 days 04:07:11	CHIBA
431004411	Cargo	YOKOSUKA	2022-09-30 18:00:18	2022-09-30 23:14:09	0 days 05:13:51	KAWASAKI
305002000	Cargo	TOKYO	2022-09-30 18:01:06	2022-09-30 20:35:48	0 days 02:34:42	KAWASAKI
352898766	Cargo	KAWASAKI	2022-09-30 18:03:34	2022-09-30 20:57:46	0 days 02:54:12	TOKYO
477010600	Cargo	TOKYO	2022-09-30 18:03:49	2022-09-30 21:14:35	0 days 03:10:46	KAWASAKI
441279000	Cargo	KOBE	2022-09-30 18:03:56	2022-09-30 22:23:50	0 days 04:19:54	NISHINOMIYA

Fig. 5. Port Information Data Frame

Once completed, the port data frame contains the following information:

- MMSI
- Port Name
- Vessel Type (Cargo/Fishing)
- Entry and Exit Times
- Duration
- Next Port Name

An example of the collected port information can be seen in Figure 5.

C. Interactive Dashboard

Due to the vast amount of resulting data from exploring vessel relationships, we decided the best way to interpret the results would be through an interactive dashboard. The dashboard contains two different tabs, one for the port traffic results and one for the interaction results. The port traffic tab allows the user to investigate the results on a country, port, and individual ship level. At the country and port level, it breaks down of the number of ships in terms of flag country, navigation status, and vessel type. In addition, the port level shows the average amount of time ships spend in the port as well as the distribution. Lastly, also displayed are statistics about which port vessels traveled to next after leaving the

current port. The ship level allows for a MMSI to be selected and then shows which ports the ship traveled to and in what order.

The interaction tab begins with a heat map that displays all of the identified interactions during the given time period. Below the heat map are six different filters that allow for exploration of the interaction results. The filters include: cargo MMSI, fishing MMSI, cargo vessel flag country, fishing vessel flag country, duration and date. Any combination of filters can be selected. For example, we could investigate the interactions between Chinese cargo vessels and Japanese fishing vessels on March 10, 2022. Whichever filters are selected, the qualifying interactions are plotted on the heat map. Following the filters are statistics on the cargo vessels (reefers) such as which reefers had multiple interactions and if those interactions were with more than one fishing vessel or country. There is also a breakdown of what countries the reefers are from. Next, is information about red flag cargo and fishing vessels. A vessel is classified as a red flag if it has a bad MMSI (either all the same number or a commonly used one), has no flag country, has been listed as a cargo and fishing vessel, had more than five interactions on a single day as found by the interaction algorithm [11], or is on the combined IUU fishing list [10]. Interactions that involved a red flag cargo vessel, fishing vessel or both are plotted for the user to see. The advantage of the dashboard is it makes the results easy to interpret and interactive.

V. IUU IDENTIFICATION USING MACHINE LEARNING

A. Item Response Theory Model

1) *Background:* Item Response Theory has a long history. The model gained popularity through the 1950s and 1960s and was mainly used in psychology. Since then IRT has expanded into other disciplines based for many types of problems [5]. The main idea of the model was to identify a latent trait that was not measurable such as intelligence, by using the visible traits, such as whether students answered the question correctly [5]. Now, IRT contains a very broad family of models but the model we selected was the Generalized Partial Credit Model (GPCM) [7]. This model allows for students to get partial credit on a question instead of having the question be either right or wrong like in the original version of the IRT model. The model also does a similar calculation to the original IRT model, but allows for different distributions based on how many points students got on the question [7]. The equation below represents the Generalized Partial Credit Model

$$P_{i,k}(\theta) = \frac{e^{\sum_{j=1}^k a_i(\theta - g_{ij})}}{\sum_{r=0}^m e^{\sum_{j=1}^r a_i(\theta - g_{ij})}}$$

where $P_{i,k}(\theta)$ is the probability that a student with ability θ would score k in the assignment i . m is the max number of points for assignment i , a_i is the discrimination parameter for assignment i , and $g_{i,j}$ which represents the difficulty for the

student to reach grade j given that they have reached grade $j - 1$ [7].

2) *Item Response Theory in IUU Fishing Context:* With the IRT framework in mind, we decided to apply the GPCM model to the problem at hand. Without truth data, we realized an IRT framework could be a possible work around for the problem. In IUU context, $Pr(i, x)$ would represent the different probabilities for item i based on vessel x 's bin which represented the vessel's "partial credit". For example, one of the questions could be how close to the nearest EEZ is the vessel. When the answer to that question is a small distance or the least amount of credit, we hope that leads to a shift in that vessel's theta. Ideally, the shift would be towards the side of the scale that contains vessels with markers of illegal fishing.

B. Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN)

1) *Background:* Density-Based Spatial Clustering Applications with Noise, or DBSCAN, is a machine learning technique used for analyzing clusters in spatial data. In contrast to other popular algorithms such as K-Means or Hierarchical Clustering, DBSCAN can recognize nonstandard clustering shapes, and thus can be a more powerful tool when analyzing a large geographical area. DBSCAN works by analyzing the radius (defined as epsilon) around a certain data entry, and searches for points that have a minimum value of other points within that boundary. These points are marked as "core" points, and serve as the basis from which the clusters will evolve. "Outlier" values, defined as those with no other points within their epsilon border, are classified as "noise" and not grouped with any other cluster. This can be particularly insightful for geospatial data, as objects can be sorted based on a given real-world distance from a certain point (in our case, other vessels).

2) *DBSCAN and IUU Fishing:* The second machine learning algorithm we explored to provide insight into IUU fishing was DBSCAN. The AIS communication data was broken into one hour chunks of data containing only fishing vessels. Before running the algorithm we assigned each AIS communication an IUU score of 0-5. Figure 6 provides a detailed explanation of each parameter used. DBSCAN was then used to cluster the AIS received during that hour based on latitude and longitude. Knee plots were used to determine the optimum epsilon value and a min points of 10 was used. Once the clusters were found, the mean IUU score of the cluster was calculated and added to the each AIS score. The purpose of this is to raise the score of surrounding ships if a majority of the vessels in the area had high scores. After the cluster mean was added, the scores were normalized on a scale of five. Scores greater than five were simply be rounded down to five. Due to the normalization, scores greater than 0.2 (1/5) are considered of interest because they are most likely committing an illegal act. AIS points above the threshold were added to a separate data frame for further analysis. DBSCAN was run a second time with a min points of 50 on the points above the threshold to

try and ascertain areas where illegal fishing is most likely to occur.

	no_flag	bad_mmsi	cargo_and_fishing	too_many_interactions	on_IUU_list
1	Flag country is listed as nan	A) mmsi only contains one unique number (ex. 1111111111) B) mmsi is a commonly made up number (123456789, 123456789, 160000000, 600600600)	vessel has listed themselves as a cargo vessel at one time and as a fishing vessel at another time	The vessel had more than 5 interactions in a single day as determined by the interaction algorithm	The vessel is on the combined IUU fishing list maintained by TM-Tracking (TMT), a Norwegian not-for-profit organisation which can be found here https://iuu-vessels.org/
0	Flag country is not listed as np.nan	mmsi does not fall in the categories of A or B from above	All AIS communication shows the same vessel type	The vessel had less than or equal to 5 interactions in a single day as determined by the interaction algorithm	The vessel is not on the IUU fishing list

Fig. 6. DBSCAN Parameters

VI. CASE STUDY: OCTOBER 1ST - OCTOBER 5TH 2022

A. Refrigeration vessels

The results from our interaction algorithm provided a lot of insight into reefer interactions during the time of October 1st - 5th. Figure 7 shows a heat map that represents all the interactions during the time frame. There are three main places interactions occurred, outside of port which is to be expected, along Russia and Japan's EEZ and in the South China Sea.

Fig. 7. Map of all Interactions Oct 1 - Oct 5 2022

There were 580 interactions involving 238 unique reefers with 208 of the reefers being valid. A valid reefer is defined as one that was not a red flag reefer and it did not interact with any red flag fishing vessels. Only valid reefers were used in the calculation of the following statistics. The average number of interactions per reefer was 1.76, and 12 different reefers were involved in two or more interactions. The most interactions by a single reefer during the five day time span was seven. The majority of reefers with multiple interactions met with multiple fishing vessels, but all reefers only met with vessels from a single country. As expected, most reefers were from nearby countries such as Japan, China, Russia, and South Korea. In total, there were 30 red flag cargo vessels and 100 red flag fishing vessels. The top issue for cargo vessels was having no flag and being represented as both a cargo and fishing vessel, while the overwhelming issue for fishing vessels was no flag country. The vast majority of interactions involving a red flag vessel occurred in the South China Sea.

B. Port Traffic

From our five day sample, we observed that the five most popular ports for both fishing and cargo vessels were Kawasaki, Kobe, Moji, Muturezima, and Mizushima, all of which totaled over 140 ships entering their boundaries within the given interval, and remaining there for at least 0.5 hours. That being said, changing the "in port" time interval from 0.5 to 3 hours results in very different results, with Fukuyama and Osaka replacing Moji and Muturezima in the top five. This likely indicates that vessels often pass through the latter two ports to arrive at their final destinations, but do not dock there frequently. By contrast, Fukuyama and Osaka tend to be more popular long-term stopping points. In most cases, the vast majority of ships in these ports identified as Japanese, although foreign ships entirely encompassed the population of the port of Niigata-ko. Of vessels flying non-Japanese flags, Panamanian vessels were the most common in an overwhelming majority of ports, followed by Hong Kong and China. It is not surprise to see a number of ships from Panama because Panama is often considered a flag of convenience. Flag of convenience means anyone can register a boat there, making certain illicit activities easier. An example visualization, for the port of Tokyo, can be seen in Figure 8.

Fig. 8. Reported Country Flags in Tokyo, Oct 1 - Oct 5 2022

For the next port results, we observed a wide range of destinations for ships travelling between locations; however, a few noticeable trends could be observed. Most vessels traveling through dense urban areas with multiple ports (e.g. Tokyo-Kawasaki-Chiba) had their "next port" result be the neighboring locality to their original starting place. Likewise, even when leaving their local cluster, vessels remained in the same general geographic radius. We believe this is because a five-day period might be too short to observe, a cargo vessel leaving, picking up fish, and returning to a different port.

C. IRT Results

The IRT results from the case study time frame are intriguing. There were 171,826 AIS points that were run through the algorithm and the parameters used in the model were whether the vessel had the same flag as the closest EEZ, how far away the vessel was from an EEZ (binned into five different groups), how long had it been since the last AIS communication of the MMSI (binned into five different groups), and if the vessel is not flying a flag. The results of the IRT model are as follows.

TABLE I
TABLE OF IRT PARAMETERS

IRT Parameter	Parameter Values	
	F1	h2
Same Flag	0.972	0.94557
Distance Bin	0.530	0.28083
No Flag	0.520	0.27045
Time Bin	-0.017	0.00029

The output in Table 1 shows the contribution of each feature in the model. F1 values are a key indicator as to which item's variance explain the variance of the latent trait. Both of the parameters that represent whether the vessel is flying a flag or not and how close the vessel is to the nearest EEZ binned in groups of five have their variances explain around 50 percent of the variance in the latent trait. The variance of the item of whether the vessel had the same flag as the closest EEZ explained 97 percent of the variance in the latent trait.

The theta scores that the IRT model produced are very good at clustering. In Figure 9, the observations that received the lowest θ scores are shown.

	mmsi	dt_static_utc	Smallest_Distance_Vector	country_eez	flag_country	Time	theta_values
968	600900000	2022-10-01 01:39:32	0.173476968	Russia		5582	-1.573762
3293	994161665	2022-10-01 02:36:01	0.268741536	Japan		1661	-1.573762
4734	994161665	2022-10-01 03:10:33	0.260820655	Japan		2072	-1.573762
7689	994161665	2022-10-01 05:11:55	0.236158676	Japan		6229	-1.573762
9047	600900000	2022-10-01 06:26:54	0.113770005	Russia		15776	-1.573762

Fig. 9. Table with Observations with the Highest Theta Scores

These observations all have the indicators of possible IUU fishing with some MMSIs being very common, not flying a flag, and the time between the last AIS communication is in the thousands of seconds.

The highest observations in terms of the θ scoring system are shown in Figure 10.

	mmsi	dt_static_utc	Smallest_Distance_Vector	country_eez	flag_country	Time	theta_values
64	431466000	2022-10-01 00:06:17	3.660083	Japan	Japan	0	1.266039
74	431594000	2022-10-01 00:06:41	10.037759	Japan	Japan	0	1.266039
87	431466000	2022-10-01 00:07:13	3.659856	Japan	Japan	56	1.266039
131	432399000	2022-10-01 00:08:49	3.601831	Japan	Japan	0	1.266039
136	431914000	2022-10-01 00:08:57	4.250274	Japan	Japan	0	1.266039

Fig. 10. Table with Observations with the Highest Theta Scores

The observations on the other side of the theta spectrum are the observations that have little to no indicators of possible

IUU fishing. The MMSIs are not as common, the vessels seem to be flying the flag that is the same as the closest EEZ, and the time between the last AIS communication is very small. However, there may be vessels that are committing acts of IUU fishing but are falsifying AIS information.

D. DBSCAN Results

Running the DBSCAN algorithm outlined in Section IV we hoped to gain insight into locations where illegal fishing is most relevant. For the dates of Oct 1 - Oct 5 we obtained the following results. Figure 11 displays the clusters that were identified while Table 2 shows the mean and number of ships in each cluster. The results confirm our initial suspicions given by the interaction results. The South China Sea is the cluster with the most ships by far. Cluster two, which is blue, has the highest cluster mean score of 0.259. These results give us a good idea of where most illegal activities occur.

Fig. 11. DBSCAN Clusters

TABLE II
TABLE OF CLUSTER STATISTICS

Number of Cluster	Cluster Values		
	Mean	AIS Points	Num Ships
0	0.224909	7943	167
1	0.258703	212	10
2	0.206203	128	4
3	0.212859	319	12
4	0.231861	359	10
5	0.208419	227	1
6	0.235561	239	7
7	0.210881	59	1
8	0.219906	53	3
9	0.217953	106	1
10	0.226962	209	25

VII. FUTURE WORK

As mentioned in Section V, both the Item Response Theory (IRT) and Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN) models provided promising results. The θ scores from the IRT model offered good insight regarding which parameters, or characteristics of a vessel, may indicate IUU activity. Similarly, DBSCAN was able to identify geospatial clusters of data where IUU activity is most likely occurring. This research provides a basis for successful future work in this field.

There are four suggestions we have to build upon this work. First, we suggest increasing the sample size across the board. Due to the widespread characteristics of IUU fishing,

more observations will only improve the results. Secondly, we suggest to increase the number of parameters in the IRT model. Again, increasing the number of parameters will improve results - given these new parameters are likely IUU indicators and are not repetitive in the model. The third area for future work may include combining the results of DBSCAN's "hot spot" clusters into the IRT model. Lastly, the creation of a classification algorithm using these results is highly anticipated. One suggestion may be using the previous work done by Padmaja, Mounika, Sowjanya, Keerthana, and Tejaswini as a framework, classifying IUU fishing by combining our results with a random forest [3].

VIII. CONCLUSION

Overall, our exploratory analysis shed light on both vessel relationships and IUU fishing patters. Not only were patterns found and analyzed but they were displayed in an easily understandable manner through an interactive dashboard. Discovering vessel relationships allowed for the development of two machine learning models that identified IUU fishing. While there is still much work to do in this area our research provides a foundation for future work.

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